

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

D1.4: First yearly documentation and minutes of project meetings

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Introduction

During the first year of the project, the project members engaged with each other through a number of different meetings. These took place via telephone, video conferencing, or face-to-face. In general, these meetings can be divided into three different categories: operational, governance/strategy, and informal.

Meeting category	Meeting type	Method(s)	Frequency
1. Operational	Work Packages	Phone, video conferencing, face-to-face	Variable depending on task at hand
	WGIS (Work Group on Identification and Standards)	Video conferencing, face-to-face	Monthly, bi-monthly
2. Governance/strategy	Project kick-off	Face-to-face (one-time)	One-off (at the project start)
	General assembly and the Project Advisory Board	Face-to-face	Yearly
	Executive Committee	Video conferencing and face-to-face	Monthly
	Steering Committee	Video conferencing and face-to-face	Every three months
3. Informal (unplanned/spontaneous)	Variable	Variable	Variable

This report documents the main content of the different types of meetings that have been realised. At the same time, this report will not reproduce the detailed minutes of each meeting, because the abundance of these precise details would not be interesting or insightful for this report's audience. Instead, we chose to use this report as an opportunity to share the current meeting organisations, important decisions and contents, as well as reflections for better execution of future meetings.

Meeting contents/minutes

During the year, the main contents/decisions of the different types of meetings have been the following:

1. Operational meetings

Work Packages

These meetings are conducted within and across Work Packages and institutions to advance operational progress. Up to now, these meetings have been held mainly by the Work Packages whose timelines fall within the first year. As noted in the above table, the methods vary from phone/video conferencing/face-to-face meetings. Some Work Packages hold regular, periodical meetings for longer-term tasks, while other Work Packages organise their meetings on an as-needed basis. In order to facilitate project coherence, the Work Packages usually include the project manager in the meetings and/or sends news and updates.

Additionally, each Work Package discusses with the project manager on a “catch-up” call each semester for a general overview and planning of the Work Package.

The content and topics are too wide and varied to be described in this report, but in essence, the results of these meetings are the decisions made to drive the project forward according to the project proposal and the deliverables/milestones timelines. In other words, the fruits of these meetings can be seen in the project deliverables and milestones, as well as the content presented in the [Governance and strategy meetings](#) (see below).

WGIS (Work Group on Identification and Standards)

The WGIS group is comprised of the project members across the consortium institutions whose tasks include (meta)data identification and standardisation. These Work Packages are primarily Work Packages 4, 5, 6, 7, and 9.

Additionally, the overall technical design (architecture and functionality) is dissected within meetings of a subgroup of the WGIS (the architecture group), consisting of members of Work Packages 5, 6, and 9.

The purpose of the group is to ensure coherence among the Work Packages, and for the project as a whole, on these topics. Participants have the opportunity to bring forth topics and progress to share, as well as to ask for feedback and discussion on issues that they are working on.

The group meets via video conferencing or face-to-face on a monthly or bi-monthly basis.

Key topics discussed in the meetings include, but are not limited, to the following:

- ▶ Metadata: discussion on the standards and the platform chosen (please see Work Package 4’s deliverables for further details) and enrichment
- ▶ Overall architecture: features and concepts (including extent of federation)
- ▶ Discussions on identification standards and process frameworks for information system work
- ▶ Topics relevant to the preliminary database merging exercise for Work Package 6 (between data of the Brussels and French stock exchanges) such as the database infrastructure and concept proposal
- ▶ Subjects related to Work Package 7 (inserting the OCR outputs into the database). Note that this topic is significant enough that this (and other important topics) are progressing through more extensive discussions in regular cross-institutional Work Package meetings.

2. Governance and strategy meetings

Executive Committee

The Executive Committee meets on a monthly basis (via video conferencing, with a face-to-face meeting every semester). The members consist of: Angelo Riva (École d’Économie de Paris), Jan Annaert (Universiteit Antwerpen), and Wolfgang König (Goethe-Universität Frankfurt). The meetings are also accompanied by the project manager (based at the École d’Économie de Paris) for purposes of alignment with the Executive Committee’s decisions with the project and the Work Packages as a whole.

Key topics from previous meetings include:

- ▶ Overview of overall strategy of the project (as well as integration of feedback from the Project Advisory Board, the General Assembly, the Steering Committee, and all of the project members)
- ▶ Ensuring the project's engagement with and utility to the European research infrastructure, and academic, public, and business communities
- ▶ Proposing key decisions on project features and direction as needed, for discussion and approval by the project members, including scientific quality of the project outputs (in the present and for the future)
- ▶ Overall governance and protocols, such as project execution, internal and external communications, as well as resource monitoring (human resources, finances, materials, etc.)
- ▶ Risk management

Steering Committee

The Steering Committee meets every three months (via video conferencing, with a face-to-face meeting every semester). The participants consist of the Work Package leaders (the Executive Committee members are thus inherently members of the Steering Committee). The Steering Committee meetings are also attended by the project manager (to ensure alignment of the project strategy among the Executive Committee, the Steering Committee, and the Work Packages), as well as other relevant person(s) for the agenda at hand (for example, if a particular topic/concept will be discussed and will be presented by a project team member). The meeting topics are governance- and strategy-related, with a greater emphasis to the technical and content implementation of the project and the consortium coordination overall.

Key topics discussed in the past meetings include:

- ▶ Ensuring long-term sustainability (operationally and governance-wise) to include in the infrastructure design
- ▶ Partnerships and collaborations with other European infrastructures and the stakeholder community
- ▶ Agreement on key design decisions and action points, such as the order of data being tested and the process to bring the technical Work Packages to fruition
- ▶ Governance issues such as legal and communication protocols, as well as agenda for Project Advisory Board and General Assembly meetings

Project kick-off

The project kick-off meeting (which included the first Project Advisory Board meeting) took place on 11th April 2018 at the École d'Économie de Paris (Paris School of Economics) (coordinating institution and Work Package 1 leader). Key parts of the programme consisted of remarks from the Executive Committee, presentations from the Work Packages, as well as experiences and perspectives from Project Advisory Board members and collaborators.

Highlighted topics include:

- ▶ Overall mission and expected impact of the EURHISFIRM project
- ▶ Preliminary strategy and execution (e.g. expected scientific and technical challenges, legal topics, governance)
- ▶ Proposed ideas and discussions on the Work Packages

Project Advisory Board (PAB) and General Assembly

The Project Advisory Board (PAB) meets yearly, in conjunction with the General Assembly. The PAB provides feedback on the project progress and advises on key strategic questions. These serve as crucial perspectives upon the project's overall direction and governance. The General Assembly is an extension of the PAB meeting, which summarises the issues discussed within the PAB and opens the discussion to the external invited guests and interested stakeholders. This meeting also includes further detailed progress per Work Package and is an important opportunity for feedback and alignment from the entire consortium on these advancements.

The first PAB and General Assembly meeting took place on 15-16 March 2019 at the Wroclaw University of Economics, following the format described above. Key topics discussed include:

- ▶ Ensuring our project's pertinence, utility, and long-term sustainability to European institutions and initiatives, including prioritisation of connecting with the larger stakeholder community and other European infrastructures
- ▶ Overall progress on the different elements of the project, technical and content-wise, including crucial conceptual questions such as striking the right balance between centralization and cost-effectiveness versus flexibility and optimisation
- ▶ Legal implications of the infrastructure design and the data in consideration, in the present and in the future
- ▶ External guests' shared experiences of working with historical financial data, and understanding their interest and stake in the EURHISFIRM project and their expected benefits from it

3. Informal discussions (unplanned/spontaneous)

As in any project, sometimes interesting ideas and discussions spring forth from unplanned/informal discussions and meetings. These collaborations and discussions happen both within and cross-institutions, especially in face-to-face meetings. This is one of the reasons that, going forward, we envision encouraging more face-to-face meetings to continue strengthening the cross-institutional collaborations which have contributed to the project's progress so far and which will continue to be vital for its success (see [Conclusions](#)).

Conclusions: going forward and reflections on future organisation

During the first year, many fruitful meetings and collaborations have taken place for the project, as described above. Going forward, we are considering two proposals to further increase the strengths of these collaborations:

- ▶ Increase face-to-face meetings among Work Package members leading key topics. This could be especially pertinent for the Work Packages involved in information systems topics as these tasks continue to develop more profoundly in the second year
- ▶ Increasing visual documentation (diagrams, pictures, etc.) to illustrate decisions made on processes. The project has maintained, within individual and at collaborative levels, mainly text-based documentation so far, as much of the first year's contents were broader and in the process of being defined. Going forward, as these decisions have become much more nuanced and precise, good visual documentation will be important supplements to the meeting records.